

SELF ESTEEM, PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT AND ANXIETY AS PREDICTORS OF CAREER DECISION-MAKING AMONG SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN EDO STATE

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ABSTRACT: This paper investigated self-esteem, parental involvement and anxiety as predictors of career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State. The research questions guided the study while three null hypotheses were formulated. This study adopted a correlation survey research design. The population of the study comprised all 20,098 senior secondary two (SS2) students from all 297 public secondary schools in Edo State. The sample size for the study consisted of 2,040 SS2 students drawn through multi-stage sampling procedure. The instrument used for data collection was through questionnaire. The questionnaire is divided into four sets. The first set is the Hare Self-esteem Scale (HSS) developed by Hare in 1985. The second set is titled “Parental Involvement Rating Scale” (PIRS) developed by Epstein and Salinas in 1993. The third set is titled “Revised Children’s Manifest Anxiety Scale (RCMAS) developed by Cecil and Bert in 1978. The fourth set is titled “Career Decision-Making Difficulties Questionnaire” (CDDQ) developed by Gati, Krausz and Osipowe in 1996. This study adopted all four sets of questionnaire which has high validity and reliability report. Linear regression was used to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The findings revealed that self-esteem significantly predicts career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State, indicating that students with higher self-esteem are more confident in making career choices. Additionally, parental involvement was found to have a strong predictive influence on students’ career decision-making, highlighting the importance of supportive family engagement. Finally, anxiety was also identified as a significant predictor. It was recommended amongst others that secondary schools in Edo State should actively involve parents in the career guidance process through regular parent-teacher conferences, career day events, and structured family engagement sessions.

Introduction

The process of career decision-making remains one of the most critical decisions individuals

make in life, especially during adolescence and young adulthood. For senior secondary school students in Edo State, this decision significantly

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influences not only their future economic stability but also their personal fulfilment, self-identity, and societal relevance. Over time, educators, policymakers, and scholars have expressed growing concern over the nature and quality of career decisions made by students, particularly because of the apparent disconnect between students' interests, capabilities, and the career paths they eventually pursue. Career decision-making refers to the process through which individuals select a profession or occupation they intend to pursue over the course of their lives. According to Johnson and Morgan (2021), career decision-making is shaped by a complex interplay of factors including individual interests, abilities, socio-economic background, parental influence, and the level of educational exposure. It is not a one-time event, but rather a continuous process that involves assessing one's values, aspirations, and long-term life goals.

Scholars have argued that career decision-making involves both deliberate and unconscious processes, incorporating cognitive reasoning as well as emotional factors (Adewale & Nwosu, 2022). As Eze and Onwuka (2023) noted, it reflects a student's aspirations, worldview, and perception of available career opportunities. Given its multidimensional nature, career decision-making is influenced by a broad range of social, psychological, and environmental factors that often operate simultaneously, shaping the direction and quality of students' future professional lives.

The importance of career decision-making in the lives of senior secondary school students cannot be overemphasised. An informed and appropriate decision at this stage can lead to a successful and fulfilling future. Thompson

(2020) asserted that sound career decision-making enables individuals to realise their full potential, achieve economic independence, and contribute positively to societal development. Furthermore, when students are guided into careers that match their innate interests and abilities, they tend to show increased motivation, academic achievement, and long-term engagement. Udo and Okoro (2021) also highlighted that early and accurate career decision-making can help reduce school dropout rates and youth unemployment, two pressing challenges in Nigeria's education sector.

Career decision-making also has significant implications for national development. According to Chukwu and Aliyu (2023), when individuals pursue careers that align with their natural strengths and preferences, the result is greater productivity, innovation, and job satisfaction. Conversely, poor career decisions can have long-lasting negative effects. Ayodele and Balogun (2020) warn that mismatches between students' personalities and chosen careers may lead to dissatisfaction, poor job performance, and even mental health issues like anxiety and depression. Students in Edo State who are compelled into careers due to parental pressure or societal expectations may experience frustration and resentment, ultimately affecting their long-term career growth (Okonkwo & Ezeani, 2022). Bello and Abubakar (2023) further added that such individuals are at risk of developing low self-esteem, negative work attitudes, and strained workplace relationships. These psychological and social dynamics suggest the need to examine key personal and familial variables—particularly self-esteem, parental involvement, and anxiety—as significant

predictors of students' career decision-making patterns.

Self-esteem, defined as an individual's evaluation of their self-worth or personal value, plays a central role in how students make career decisions. Students with high self-esteem are more likely to believe in their abilities, explore a broader range of career options, and commit to goals aligned with their values and interests. In contrast, students with low self-esteem may doubt their competencies, resulting in indecisiveness or the tendency to adopt externally imposed career paths. As noted by Ifedioramma and Anyamene (2025), self-esteem influences confidence in decision-making, and later research by Edeh (2019) confirmed that Nigerian students with higher self-esteem reported greater clarity and satisfaction in their career choices. In Edo State, where competition for limited career opportunities can be intense, students with low self-esteem may experience career paralysis, opting for “safe” or socially approved careers rather than those that align with their aptitudes. Consequently, addressing self-esteem is vital for empowering students to make autonomous and fulfilling career decisions. Studies have shown that self-esteem plays a vital role in enhancing students' confidence and decision-making ability. For example, Adekeye, Adenusi, Ahmadu and Okojide (2017) found that self-esteem significantly predicted career maturity among students in Southwestern Nigeria. Similarly, in Edo State, Ifedioramma and Anyamene (2025) found that students with high self-esteem also performed better academically, suggesting readiness for sound vocational choices. However, contrasting findings by Okafor and

Akpochafo (2022) indicated that self-esteem alone may not always reduce career decision-making difficulties, particularly when other external pressures are present.

Closely related to self-esteem is the influence of parental involvement, which significantly shapes how students approach career decision-making. Parental involvement includes the extent to which parents support, guide, or control their children's career aspirations. While positive parental engagement can provide students with the resources, encouragement, and emotional stability needed to explore and pursue meaningful careers, over-involvement—especially in the form of coercion—can lead to conflict and psychological distress. According to Ukaegbu (2017), Nigerian parents often play a dominant role in selecting careers for their children, frequently pushing them towards medicine, law, or engineering regardless of personal interest. This trend is evident in many secondary schools in Edo State, where students often report feeling compelled to follow predetermined paths. When parental involvement becomes prescriptive rather than supportive, it may suppress students' autonomy, lower self-esteem, and increase the risk of anxiety and poor career alignment (Obiunu, 2015). Adebayo and Umar (2021) reported that supportive parental guidance positively predicted career decision satisfaction. In contrast, Onyekwere and Nwosu (2024) observed a weak link between parenting styles and career indecision, highlighting that the quality of parental engagement.

Anxiety, particularly decision-making anxiety, is another critical psychological factor that predicts students' ability to choose suitable careers.

Career decision-making is inherently stressful, especially for adolescents navigating complex social expectations, economic constraints, and academic pressures. According to Germeijs and De Boeck (2002), students experiencing career decision-making difficulties often report high levels of anxiety, which may manifest in procrastination, avoidance behaviors, or rushed choices. In the Nigerian context, academic competition, societal expectations, and limited job opportunities exacerbate these anxieties. Edo State students, for example, may feel overwhelmed by the need to secure admission into competitive fields, even when these options do not align with their interests. Eze (2019) observed that heightened anxiety levels among senior secondary students were negatively correlated with career decision-making self-efficacy, suggesting that unaddressed anxiety can impair rational thinking, reduce confidence, and lead to regretful career paths.

Amidst the compelling interplay between self-esteem, parental involvement, and anxiety in shaping students' career decision-making, the researcher was motivated to embark on this study by the growing concern over the persistent mismatch between students' chosen careers and their actual interests, capabilities, and emotional readiness—particularly in Edo State, Nigeria. Observations from local schools and guidance counselors revealed that many senior secondary school students often express uncertainty, confusion, and distress when confronted with career choices. These challenges are frequently compounded by socio-cultural expectations, parental pressure, low self-worth, and psychological stress. Despite existing educational policies and career guidance

frameworks, a significant number of students continue to make career decisions that do not align with their personalities or long-term aspirations. This therefore prompted the study to investigate self-esteem, parental involvement and anxiety as predictors of career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State.

Statement of the Problem

In recent times, concerns about the quality of career decisions made by senior secondary school students in Nigeria have become more pronounced, particularly in Edo State. Teachers, school counsellors, and even parents have observed that a significant number of students approach career choices with confusion, low confidence, and emotional instability. Many students display hesitation and fear when required to decide on future career paths, and this indecision often leads to frustration, poor academic performance, and misalignment between career aspirations and individual potentials. One major factor underlying these challenges is low self-esteem. Teachers report that students who exhibit low confidence in their abilities tend to avoid challenging career paths, not because of a lack of capacity, but because they underestimate their worth and fear failure. These students are often overly dependent on external validation and may shy away from making independent, informed decisions about their future.

In addition, parental involvement has also emerged as a critical influence. Many parents in Edo State still insist on choosing careers for their children, motivated by prestige, income potential, or family expectations, without considering the children's interests or strengths.

School counsellors lament that students frequently attend career counselling sessions only to express frustration at having no say in decisions about their own future. Some parents, on the other hand, are entirely uninvolved, leaving students to grapple with complex career decisions without adequate guidance or emotional support. Anxiety further complicates this situation. Teachers and guidance counsellors note that students preparing for external examinations and post-secondary life often show signs of worry, restlessness, and mental fatigue. For some, the fear of making the “wrong” choice paralyzes decision-making altogether. This persistent anxiety affects their mental clarity and often leads to hasty, ill-informed, or externally influenced choices that do not reflect their genuine aspirations or capabilities.

Given these observations, it is evident that low self-esteem, poor or misdirected parental involvement, and anxiety are central predictors of poor career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State. Yet, there appears to be limited empirical focus on how these psychological and social variables jointly influence students’ readiness to make sound career decisions. This study is therefore driven by the need to examine the predictive roles of self-esteem, parental involvement, and anxiety in the career decision-making of students in Edo State. In specific terms, this study investigated how:

1. Self-esteem predicts career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State

2. Parental involvement predicts career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State

3. Anxiety predicts career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the prediction between self-esteem and career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State?

2. What is the prediction between parental involvement and career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State?

3. What is the prediction between anxiety and career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State?

Hypotheses

Ho1: Self-esteem does not significantly predict career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State

Ho2: Parental involvement does not significantly predict career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State

Ho3: Anxiety does not significantly predict career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State

Method

This study was carried out in Edo State. This study adopted a correlation survey research design. The population of the study comprised all 20,098 senior secondary two (SS2) students from all 297 public secondary schools in Edo State. The sample size for the study consisted of 2,040 SS2 students drawn through multi-stage sampling procedure. The instrument used for data collection was through questionnaire. The

questionnaire is divided into four sets. The first set is the Hare Self-esteem Scale (HSS) developed by Hare in 1985. Hare Self-esteem Scale is a self-esteem report psychometric scale which was developed to measure individual's self-esteem as it relates to interaction with peers, in homes and schools. The Hare Self-esteem Scale for this study contains 30 items which are directed towards measuring students' level of self-esteem. The instrument is on a four-point scales of strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree. This scale was adopted for this study because it is highly related to students' self-esteem, was revalidated for the Nigerian population and has been used by indigenous researchers with good results (Okafor, Obi & Oguzie, 2018; Nwokolo & Oguzie, 2021).

The second set is titled "Parental Involvement Rating Scale" (PIRS) developed by Epstein and Salinas in 1993. The Parental Involvement Rating Scale (PIRS) developed by Epstein and Salinas (1993) is designed to measure the extent, quality, and nature of parental involvement in a child's education and quantifies how much influence parents exert on their children's academic paths. The questionnaire comprises 28 Likert-type items in total. Though originally developed in the U.S., the scale has been adapted and validated for various cultural settings and educational contexts, including primary and secondary schools

The third set is titled "Revised Children's Manifest Anxiety Scale (RCMAS) developed by Cecil and Bert in 1978. The RCMAS is a widely used self-report inventory designed to assess generalized, social, and performance-related

anxiety in adolescents (ages 6–19). It is based on manifest anxiety theory and aims to capture the student's subjective experience of anxiety—including physiological arousal, worry, and concentration difficulties—while detecting response bias through a defensiveness (lie) subscale. It is a 28-item instrument with a ratings of Yes or No to each statement. The original RCMAS demonstrated excellent internal consistency: a KR20 estimate of 0.85 and strong factor validity across diverse samples (grades 1–12).

The fourth set is titled "Career Decision-Making Difficulties Questionnaire" (CDDQ) developed by Gati, Krausz and Osipow in 1996. The CDDQ is a diagnostic self-report scale designed to identify and quantify the specific difficulties that adolescents encounter during career decision-making. It is grounded in the decision-theory taxonomy proposed by Gati et al., which recognizes persistent hurdles such as lack of readiness, lack of accurate information, and inconsistent information usage within vocational choice behaviour. It consists of 34 psychometrically balanced items, plus 2 validity indicators with a 9-point rating scale ranging from "1 = Does not describe me at all" to "9 = Describes me very well". Median Cronbach's alpha coefficients range from .68 to .84 across subscales, while the total score exhibits alpha between .87 and .96, demonstrating strong internal consistency. Test-retest correlations fall between .67 and .80, indicating temporal stability. Linear regression was used to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level.

Results**Table 1: Linear regression on the prediction between self-esteem and career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State**

Linear Regression	R	R²	B	t	a.level	p-value
	.732 ^a	.536	.854	7.608	.05	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), Self-esteem						
b. Dependent: career decision-making						

The Table 1 provides a linear regression analysis on the prediction between self-esteem and career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State. The beta coefficient of 0.854 shows a strong prediction between self-esteem and career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State. The R² value of 0.536 means that

self-esteem explains about 53.6% of the variation in the career decision-making.

In testing the null hypothesis, the t-value of 7.608 with a p-value of 0.000 (which is less than the alpha level of 0.05) indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that self-esteem significantly predict career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State.

Table 2: Linear regression on the prediction between parental involvement and career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State

Linear Regression	R	R²	B	t	a.level	p-value
	.589 ^a	.347	.618	8.116	0.05	0.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), parental involvement						
b. Dependent: career decision-making						

Data in Table 2 reveals a linear regression on the prediction between parental involvement and career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State. The beta coefficient of 0.618 shows a strong prediction between parental involvement and career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State. The R² value of 0.589 means that parental involvement explains

about 58.9% of the variation in the career decision-making.

In testing the null hypothesis, the t-value of 8.116 with a p-value of 0.000 (which is less than the alpha level of 0.05) indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that parental involvement significantly predicted career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State.

Table 3: Linear regression: Linear regression on the prediction between anxiety and career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State

Linear Regression	R	R²	B	t	a.level	p-value
	.822 ^a	.676	.717	22.930	0.05	0.001

a. Predictors: (Constant), Anxiety
b. Dependent: career decision-making

Data in Table 3 reveals a linear regression on the prediction between anxiety and career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State. The beta coefficient of 0.717 shows a strong prediction between anxiety and career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State. The R² value of 0.676 means that anxiety explains about 67.6% of the variation in the career decision-making. In testing the null hypothesis, the t-value of 23.930 with a p-value of 0.000 (which is less than the alpha level of 0.05) indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that anxiety significantly predicted career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State.

Discussion of Findings

The finding in research question one revealed that there is a strong prediction between self-esteem and career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State. This finding means that a statistical relationship where self-esteem levels reliably forecast or influence students' ability to make career-related decisions. In research terms, this suggests that self-esteem, as a psychological construct reflecting an individual's sense of self-worth and confidence, plays a substantial role in how students approach and finalize choices about their future careers. This finding

supported that of Li, Wu and Chen (2015) agreed that high self-esteem predicted lower career uncertainty, and autonomy support fully mediated this path. Those with stronger self-esteem chose majors for self-concordance, leading to lower indecision. The finding of Okorie, Nwankwo, Iwuala and Okolie (2023) reported that self-esteem positively predicted career certainty, both directly and indirectly via career decision self-efficacy.

The corresponding hypothesis revealed that self-esteem significantly predict career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State. The finding agreed with that of Abomah (2014) and Okorie et al (2023) that there is a statistically significant association between self-esteem and clarity of career choice. The finding in research question two revealed that there is a strong prediction between parental involvement and career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State. This finding means that a statistically significant association wherein the level of parental engagement in students' academic and personal lives reliably influences their ability to make informed and confident career choices. In research terms, this suggests that parental involvement, encompassing actions such as guidance, emotional support, and resource provision, serves as a critical

determinant of students' career decision-making. This finding aligned with the finding of Ezeani, Ogu and Sabboh (2023) which found a positive relationship between parental involvement and students' career decision-making. The finding of Osaro (2024) reported high positive correlation coefficients between dimensions of parental involvement (parental expectation, support, parent-child relationship) and students' career aspirations.

The corresponding hypothesis revealed that parental involvement significantly predicted career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State. This finding opposed that of Salami and Aremu (2007) that that maternal attachment and psychological separation individually and positively predicted students' career information-seeking, whereas the combined predictor from father attachment/separation scales did not reach significance. This finding reported that while socio-economic status was significantly associated with career choice, the parents' level of formal education showed no significant relationship with the students' career choices.

The finding in research question three revealed that there is a strong prediction between anxiety and career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State. This finding revealed that this suggests that anxiety, as a psychological construct characterized by feelings of unease, worry, or fear, significantly impacts students' ability to make informed, confident, and autonomous career choices. This finding opposed that of Yalcin and Koyuncu (2024) that moderate positive correlations between anxiety dimensions and all aspects of decision-making difficulties (e.g. internal

conflict, lack of self-knowledge, irrational beliefs). The finding of Isik (2012) reported that was found to be a significant negative predictor of overall self-efficacy; importantly, trait anxiety remained a predictor even after controlling for positive affect. The differences in these findings can be attributed to several methodological, contextual, and theoretical factors

The corresponding hypothesis revealed that anxiety significantly predicted career decision-making among senior secondary school students in Edo State. This finding agreed with that of Yalcin and Koyuncu (2024) that anxiety dimensions jointly predicted about 35 % of variance in overall decision difficulty.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is evident that self-esteem, parental involvement, and anxiety play critical roles in shaping the career decision-making patterns of senior secondary school students in Edo State. The study revealed that students with higher self-esteem are more likely to make confident and informed career decisions, emphasizing the importance of nurturing positive self-perception in adolescence. Additionally, the strong predictive influence of parental involvement underscores the need for active parental guidance and support during this pivotal stage of students' academic and vocational development. Conversely, the finding that anxiety strongly predicts career decision-making highlights the detrimental impact of psychological distress on students' ability to make clear and purposeful career choices.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. School administrators and guidance counsellors integrate self-esteem enhancement programs into the school curriculum. These could include life skills workshops, peer mentoring, confidence-building activities, and recognition systems that promote students' sense of self-worth. Teachers should also adopt affirmative feedback strategies that encourage students to believe in their capabilities, especially in career-related tasks.

2. Public secondary schools in Edo State should actively involve parents in the career guidance process through regular parent-teacher conferences, career day events, and structured family engagement sessions. Educational stakeholders should also conduct

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parental orientation programs to equip parents with the skills and knowledge needed to support their children's career aspirations without imposing their personal preferences.

3. It is recommended that schools employ trained psychologists or counsellors to help students manage career-related anxiety and stress. There should be routine mental health screenings and individual or group counselling sessions to address career fears, uncertainties, and emotional blockages. Additionally, integrating relaxation techniques, mindfulness sessions, and resilience-building curricula can help students cope with anxiety and make sound career decisions

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